

ai-pam-pipeline

A modular, YAML-driven full framework for cetacean vocalization AI detection in passive acoustic monitoring

Reference Manual

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S1. Software Installation and Environment

This section covers installation on three target environments: a local workstation (Linux/macOS/Windows).

S1.1 System Requirements

Requirement	Minimum	Recommended
Python	3.9	3.11
RAM	8 GB	16 GB
Disk (Oltremare dataset + spectrograms)	50 GB	80 GB

Requirement	Minimum	Recommended
OS	Linux, macOS, Windows 10+	Ubuntu 22.04 LTS
GPU	—	NVIDIA, CUDA 11.8+

GPU acceleration is optional but strongly recommended for Stage 5 training. Preprocessing (Stages 1–4) is CPU-bound and does not benefit from GPU. On a eight-core CPU core, preprocessing the full Oltremare corpus takes approximately 25 minutes; training one 10-fold cross-validation run takes approximately 25–40 minutes for each fold without GPU.

S1.2 Installation

Clone or download the repository.

The versioned release is available on Zenodo at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19860736>. Alternatively, clone the development repository:

```
git clone https://github.com/roccodm/ai-pam-pipeline
cd ai-pam-pipeline
```

Create and activate a virtual environment.

A dedicated virtual environment isolates the toolkit dependencies from the system Python installation and is strongly recommended:

```
python3 -m venv .venv
source .venv/bin/activate      # Linux / macOS
# .venv\Scripts\activate      # Windows PowerShell
```

Install dependencies.

```
pip install --upgrade pip
pip install -r requirements.txt
```

The `requirements.txt` file is organised into three dependency groups:

Group	Packages	Required for
Core	soundfile, scipy, numpy, Pillow, matplotlib, pyyaml	Stages 1–4
Training	tensorflow ≥ 2.12, scikit-learn	Stages 5–6
Dev	pytest, pytest-cov	Test suite
Utils	fpdf2 ≥ 2.7	Spectrogram exporter

To install all the dependencies:

```
pip install -r requirements.txt
```

Verify the installation.

```
python -m pytest tests/ -v
```

All tests should pass. A failed import of `tensorflow` on a preprocessing-only node is expected if the training group was not installed.

GPU support (optional).

If a CUDA-compatible GPU is available, install the GPU build of TensorFlow:

```
pip install tensorflow[and-cuda]
```

Verify GPU visibility before running training:

```
python -c "import tensorflow as tf;
print(tf.config.list_physical_devices('GPU'))"
```

An empty list indicates that TensorFlow is running in CPU-only mode.

S2. Configuration System

S2.1 Two-level YAML Architecture

The *ai-pam-pipeline* framework utilizes a single YAML configuration file designed to provide a comprehensive description of the experimental setup. This file is organized into global configuration blocks—`experiment_meta`, `input`, `output`, and `report`—followed by specific parameter sections dedicated to each of the six pipeline stages, which are detailed in the subsequent sections of this document.

Two basic CNN models are included in the `conf/` directory (`binary_cnn.yaml`, `multiclass_cnn.yaml`). However, the framework is flexible, allowing user-defined configuration files to be stored at any location within the filesystem.

The system relies on a dual-layer configuration logic involving a **Master Configuration** and a **Project Configuration**:

- **Master Configuration (`master-config.yaml`):** Located strictly within the `conf/` directory, this file serves as the global schema. It contains an exhaustive list of all available parameters, each assigned a robust default value. The `master-config.yaml` is extensively commented to serve as a primary reference for the framework's capabilities.
- **User-Defined Configuration:** This file contains experiment-specific overrides. During execution, the framework performs a merge operation between the user-defined file and the master-config. User settings take precedence; default values from the master configuration are only injected when specific keys are absent from the user-defined file.

Best Practices and Validation:

For initiating new experiments, the recommended workflow is to clone the `master-config.yaml` into a new project file and modify the parameters according to the experimental requirements.

The framework includes a **validation layer** that monitors the merging process. Any structural inconsistencies—specifically configuration keys present in the user file but missing from the master schema—are detected and flagged as diagnostic errors. Consequently, direct modification of the `master-config.yaml` is strongly discouraged to maintain the integrity of the validation system.

S2.2 Experiment Reproducibility

To ensure full experimental tracking and reproducibility, the framework automatically exports a `run_config.yaml` file—representing the final result of the merge between the project configuration and the master configuration—into the exported spectrograms folder.

In this way, every generation of spectrograms, whether for training or cross-testing, is clearly linked to its complete preparation settings. This allows for a rigorous verification of parameter consistency by comparing the `run_config.yaml` files from different output directories.

Specifically, to guarantee the integrity of cross-domain evaluations, all spectrogram generation parameters must be identical. By maintaining this “digital twin” of the configuration alongside the data, the *ai-pam-pipeline* effectively prevents training-serving skew and facilitates the validation of results by independent researchers.

S2.3 Global parameter blocks

The YAML configuration file features global parameters that, for convenience, are typically placed at the top of the document. These settings govern the general input/output operations, define system paths, and provide bookkeeping metadata to describe the experiment.

1. `experiment_meta`

This block is for human-readable bookkeeping only and is not actively used by any processing stage.

Key	Type	Description
<code>name</code>	str	Experiment identifier
<code>version</code>	str	Version tag
<code>description</code>	str	Free-text description

These fields can be freely customized by the user. Maintaining accurate and detailed metadata is highly recommended, as it proves particularly advantageous for tracking and cataloging iterative runs with varying parameter combinations.

2. `input`

Locates the raw acoustic data and their corresponding annotations.

Key	Default	Description
<code>audio_dir</code>	<code>./data/audio</code>	Directory containing audio files
<code>label_dir</code>	<code>./data/labels</code>	Directory containing annotation files
<code>audio_glob</code>	<code>*.wav</code>	Glob pattern applied within <code>audio_dir</code>
<code>label_glob</code>	<code>*.txt</code>	Glob pattern applied within <code>label_dir</code>

These directories specify the paths to the original acoustic recordings and their corresponding label files. Labels are expected in TSV (Tab-Separated Values) format

(`<start_offset>\t<end_offset>\t<label>`), which matches the standard annotation output of PAM analysis tools like Audacity.

Pairing between audio and labels is executed by filename stem: `recording_01.wav` is paired with `recording_01.txt`. Files with no matching counterpart are skipped, and a warning is logged.

Supported Audio Formats: The framework supports all audio formats handled by the underlying `soundfile` library. You can verify the available formats in your specific environment using the following Python snippet:

```
>>> import soundfile
>>> soundfile.available_formats()
{'AIFF': 'AIFF (Apple/SGI)', 'AU': 'AU (Sun/NeXT)', 'AVR': 'AVR (Audio Visual
Research)',
 'CAF': 'CAF (Apple Core Audio File)', 'FLAC': 'FLAC (Free Lossless Audio Codec)',
 'HTK': 'HTK (HMM Tool Kit)', 'SVX': 'IFF (Amiga IFF/SVX8/SV16)', 'MAT4': 'MAT4
(GNU Octave 2.0 / Matlab 4.2)',
 'MAT5': 'MAT5 (GNU Octave 2.1 / Matlab 5.0)', 'MPC2K': 'MPC (Akai MPC 2k)',
 'MP3': 'MPEG-1/2 Audio',
 'OGG': 'OGG (OGG Container format)', 'PAF': 'PAF (Ensoniq PARIS)', 'PVF': 'PVF
(Portable Voice Format)',
 'RAW': 'RAW (header-less)', 'RF64': 'RF64 (RIFF 64)', 'SD2': 'SD2 (Sound Designer
II)',
 'SDS': 'SDS (Midi Sample Dump Standard)', 'IRCAM': 'SF (Berkeley/IRCAM/CARL)',
 'VOC': 'VOC (Creative Labs)',
 'W64': 'W64 (SoundFoundry WAVE 64)', 'WAV': 'WAV (Microsoft)', 'NIST': 'WAV (NIST
Sphere)',
 'WAVEX': 'WAVEX (Microsoft)', 'WVE': 'WVE (Psion Series 3)', 'XI': 'XI
(FastTracker 2)'}
```

3. output

This section defines the target directories for exporting data that will be reused in subsequent pipeline stages or external analyses.

Key	Default	Description
<code>spectrogram_dir</code>	<code>./outputs/spectrograms</code>	Root directory for generated spectrogram images
<code>export_dir</code>	<code>null</code>	Raw audio segment export directory; <code>null</code> = disabled

Specifically, this block allows the user to define paths for the generated 2D spectrograms and/or the isolated raw audio segments. Exporting raw segments is particularly useful for external auditory inspection of the training samples, or for workflows that train 1D-CNN models directly on raw audio waveforms rather than spectrogram images.

Images are written following a strict taxonomic hierarchy:

`<spectrogram_dir>/<class_name>/<class>-<label>-<stem>-<offset>.png`. When `export_dir` is set, the corresponding processed audio segment is also written as a WAV file with an identical naming convention.

Note: For the training script (`ai_pam_train.py`) to successfully locate the images produced during the preprocessing phase (`ai_pam_preprocessing.py`), the parameter

`pipeline.stage_5.output.dataset_dir` must point to the exact same path defined in `output.spectrogram_dir`.

4. `report`

Controls the verbosity and destination of console and file reporting.

Key	Default	Description
<code>report_dir</code>	<code>./outputs/reports</code>	Directory for generated reports
<code>summary_report</code>	<code>true</code>	Write a lightweight per-stage summary
<code>full_report</code>	<code>false</code>	Write an extended report with per-file detail

S3. Stage 1 — Audio I/O (`lib/ai_pam_audio.py`)

Stage 1 is responsible for reading audio files, selecting or mixing channels, optionally resampling to a target rate, and applying amplitude normalisation before the signal is passed to the spectrogram generation stage. The three parameters that govern this stage are listed in the table below, followed by a detailed discussion of each.

Parameter	Default	Description
<code>stage_1.resample_hz</code>	<code>null</code>	Target sample rate in Hz; <code>null</code> = retain native rate
<code>stage_1.channel</code>	<code>null</code>	Channel selection; <code>null</code> = mix to mono; integer = zero-based channel index
<code>stage_1.normalize</code>	<code>null</code>	Amplitude normalisation mode: <code>null</code> , <code>"peak"</code> , or <code>"rms"</code>

S3.1 Memory-efficient seek-based reading

A PAM deployment typically produces continuous recordings of 5 to 60 minutes, often stored as multi-gigabyte WAV or FLAC files. Loading such files entirely into memory for each extraction would be prohibitively expensive and would impose an unnecessary upper bound on the size of the corpus that can be processed on a standard workstation.

`lib/ai_pam_audio.py` avoids this by implementing **seek-based segment extraction**: for each annotated event, the reader opens the file, seeks directly to the frame offset corresponding to the event start time, and reads only the samples spanning `[t_start, t_end]`. The file handle is then closed. Peak RAM consumption at any given moment is therefore proportional to the duration of the longest annotated segment — typically a few seconds — rather than to the total file duration.

S3.2 Channel selection

PAM deployments frequently involve multi-channel recordings: stereo hydrophone pairs, towed arrays, or multi-element sensor networks are all common in cetacean monitoring. The `channel` parameter controls how multi-channel files are handled.

Value	Behaviour
<code>null</code>	Mix all channels to mono by arithmetic mean (default)
<code>0</code>	Extract channel 0 (first channel, zero-based index)
<code>1</code>	Extract channel 1 (second channel)
<code>N</code>	Extract channel N

When `null` is set, all channels are averaged sample-by-sample before further processing. This is appropriate when all channels provide independent hydrophone signals of comparable quality and the goal is to maximise SNR through averaging.

When a specific channel index is provided, only that channel is extracted and the others are discarded. This is the correct choice when channels differ in quality, when a specific hydrophone orientation is preferred, or when the file contains channels that are not acoustic recordings (e.g., GPS pulse tracks or trigger signals).

Example — DCLDE 2022 cross-test dataset. The DCLDE Oahu recordings can be used for cross-domain evaluation. A subset containing bottlenose dolphin vocalizations is corresponds to acoustic detection number 46 (15 July 2017, 11:09–11:24 UTC) contains multiple tracks recorded simultaneously by different array elements. Track 3 was selected for annotation and testing based on signal quality, and was extracted by setting `stage_1.channel: 3` in the cross-test preprocessing configuration. Processing only the selected track avoids generating redundant spectrogram datasets from all array elements and keeps the cross-test set directly comparable to the annotated sample set.

S3.3 Resampling

Value	Behaviour
<code>null</code>	Retain the native sampling rate of the file (recommended)
integer Hz	Resample all extracted segments to the specified rate

Resampling is rarely needed when the training and cross-test datasets share the same hardware and sampling rate, but becomes necessary when integrating recordings from different monitoring systems or when a model trained at one rate must be applied to data collected at another.

Retaining the native rate (`null`) is always preferred when possible, as resampling introduces mild spectral artefacts and increases processing time. If resampling is required, it should be applied identically to all datasets used in the same experimental run and recorded in the `run_config.yaml` alongside the other stage parameters.

S3.4 Amplitude normalisation

Amplitude normalisation adjusts the signal level of each extracted segment before spectrogram computation. It is applied per-segment, after any resampling, and operates on the 1D audio waveform.

Value	Behaviour	Recommended use
<code>null</code>	No normalisation; raw amplitude values passed to STFT	When recordings are already gain-matched or when absolute level information is meaningful
<code>"peak"</code>	Divide all samples by $\max(\text{abs}(x))$; output range $[-1, 1]$	When recording gain varies across sessions or deployments
<code>"rms"</code>	Scale samples so that $\text{RMS}(x) = 1$; preserves waveform shape	When SNR varies systematically across event types or distances

Peak normalisation anchors every segment to the same maximum amplitude regardless of absolute signal level. It is effective when the dynamic range of vocalizations is broad — for example, when the same species is recorded at widely varying distances — and when inter-session gain differences would otherwise produce inconsistent spectrogram brightness. The drawback is that it amplifies quiet segments, including those dominated by noise, to the same peak level as strong vocalization segments, which may reduce the apparent SNR contrast between classes.

RMS normalisation scales each segment to unit root-mean-square energy. Because the RMS is an energy measure rather than a peak measure, it is less sensitive to brief transients and more representative of the overall signal power in the window. It is preferred when the goal is to equalize the perceived loudness of events rather than their peak amplitude, and is particularly appropriate for continuous tonal vocalizations such as whistles, where energy is distributed across the duration of the call.

Neither mode alters the waveform shape or the relative frequency content; only the amplitude scale changes. Both are therefore spectrally neutral and do not affect the time–frequency structure of the resulting spectrogram. The choice between the two is dataset-dependent: when in doubt, running the preprocessing with `null` and inspecting the resulting spectrogram brightness distribution across classes is a practical diagnostic step.

Important: the normalisation mode must be identical across the training and cross-test preprocessing runs. A mismatch produces a systematic input distribution shift between training and inference, which can cause significant recall degradation without any corresponding change in precision — a failure mode that is difficult to diagnose without examining the `run_config.yaml` files from both runs side by side.

S4. Stage 2 — Label Parsing, Segmentation, and Windowing

([lib/ai_pam_segment.py](#))

Stage 2 is the most structurally complex stage of the pipeline. It reads the Audacity label files produced in Stage 1, maps the annotations onto a discrete timeline, applies exclusion zone logic to remove windows that would contaminate one class with the signal of another, performs binary erosion to trim residual boundary fragments, and finally extracts the set of audio windows that will be rendered as spectrogram images in Stage 3.

The full processing chain for each class is:

For each processed audio file, the pipeline produces a per-file report and a timeline visualisation showing the annotation state at each step of the chain. An example is shown in Figure S1 below.

Figure S1: Timeline visualisation for class C1 (whistles) from a 225-second segment of the Oltremare corpus. Each horizontal band shows the annotation state at one step of the Stage 2 processing chain. MW and W rows show the raw Audacity annotations; C1_raw is their union before any filtering; FB and NOISE rows show the exclusion sources; C1_post_excl is the C1 signal after exclusion zone subtraction; C1_eroded is the final sampling domain after binary erosion. Green segments in C1_eroded are the intervals from which spectrogram windows are extracted.

Reading the figure from top to bottom traces the progressive refinement of the usable C1 signal. The MW and W rows show all whistle-type annotations present in the file, some of which co-occur with FB (feeding buzz) or NOISE events. After exclusion zone application (C1_post_excl, blue), the portions of C1 that temporally overlapped with excluded classes are removed, often reducing a long annotation span to a shorter usable fragment or eliminating it entirely. Binary erosion (C1_eroded, green) then contracts each surviving fragment at both ends, removing the thin boundary slices that may still contain mixed-class signal. Only the green segments are eligible for window extraction.

S4.1 Timeline discretisation

Parameter	Default	Description
<code>stage_2.tl_step</code>	<code>0.05</code>	Frame duration in seconds for the discrete timeline

All label-file timestamps are converted to integer frame indices by dividing by `tl_step` and rounding. The resulting integer-valued label matrix (one row per annotation class, one column per frame) is the internal representation on which all subsequent operations — exclusion, erosion, and RLE segmentation — are performed. Floating-point accumulation errors in the label file timestamps are absorbed by this discretisation step.

Smaller `tl_step` values produce finer temporal granularity, which improves the precision of exclusion zone boundaries and erosion edges, at the cost of proportionally larger label matrices. Values between 0.02 and 0.10 s are suitable for most PAM applications.

S4.2 Class definitions

The `stage_2.classes` key is the only parameter that **must** be defined in the project file; it has no meaningful default in `master_config.yaml`. This design reflects the fact that the class taxonomy is intrinsically experiment-specific: the same audio corpus can be used to train a binary whistle detector, a multiclass vocalization classifier, or a noise characterisation model simply by changing the class definitions in the YAML file, without modifying any code or reprocessing the raw audio.

Each class entry specifies four fields:

Field	Type	Description
<code>include</code>	<code>list[str]</code>	Audacity label strings treated as positive signal for this class
<code>exclude</code>	<code>list[str]</code>	Audacity label strings that generate exclusion zones; windows overlapping these labels are discarded
<code>min_duration</code>	<code>float</code>	Minimum event duration in seconds; shorter events are filtered before discretisation, and the same value is used as the binary erosion kernel radius
<code>augmentation_scroll</code>	<code>bool null</code>	Per-class scroll override: <code>true</code> or <code>false</code> overrides the global flag; <code>null</code> inherits the global setting

The `include` list defines what counts as a positive event for that class. For C1 (whistles) in the binary experiment, this is `["W", "MW"]`: both single-whistle and multi-whistle annotations contribute positive windows. For C0 (noise), it is `["NOISE"]`.

The `exclude` list defines which co-occurring annotations make a window untrustworthy for that class. For C1, `["NOISE", "FB"]` means that any window whose time span overlaps a NOISE or FB annotation — even partially — is flagged for removal. The symmetric question (“should C0 exclude W and MW?”) is also answered in the YAML: the C0 entry lists `["W", "MW", "W?"]` as exclusions, so noise windows that contain even brief whistle activity are discarded from the negative class. This bidirectional exclusion is what gives the segmentation its class-separating power.

S4.3 Windowing parameters

Parameter	Default	Description
<code>stage_2.as_len</code>	0.8	Analysis window duration in seconds
<code>stage_2.as_overlap</code>	0.5	Fractional overlap between consecutive windows
<code>stage_2.exclude_overlaps</code>	true	Discard any window whose time span overlaps an exclusion zone
<code>stage_2.center_short_events</code>	true	Represent events shorter than <code>as_len</code> with a single centred window

The hop size in seconds is $\text{hop} = \text{as_len} \times (1 - \text{as_overlap})$. Using the default values (0.8 s, 50% overlap), the hop is 0.4 s, meaning a new window starts every 400 ms along each eligible segment. The choice of 0.8 s was motivated by the typical duration of *T. truncatus* whistle contours at the Oltremare site; other species or recording scenarios may require different window lengths.

`center_short_events: true` applies when an annotated event is shorter than `as_len`. Rather than generating a window that places the signal at an arbitrary position within the frame — which would depend on the event’s absolute timing in the recording — the pipeline generates a single window in which the event is temporally centred. This ensures that all short vocalizations appear at a consistent spatial position within the spectrogram image, which improves training stability and makes the learned features position-invariant with respect to event timing. The default value `true` is recommended for all new experiments.

S4.4 Exclusion zone logic and binary erosion

The exclusion mechanism operates in two sequential steps, both illustrated in Figure S1.

Step 1 — Exclusion zone application. For each class, every label in the `exclude` list is looked up in the label matrix. Its active frames are dilated by a padding margin equal to the hop size ($\text{as_len} \times (1 - \text{as_overlap})$) applied symmetrically around each annotation boundary. The resulting padded rows are combined into a composite exclusion mask, and any frame in the target class that overlaps this mask is suppressed. The padding margin ensures that windows starting just before or just after an excluded event do not contain residual signal from that event at their edges.

Step 2 — Binary erosion. After exclusion, the surviving active spans of the target class may still contain short fragments at their boundaries that are too brief to yield a clean window of the required duration. Binary erosion with a structuring element of length $\text{ceil}(\text{min_duration} / \text{tl_step})$

contracts each contiguous active span at both ends, eliminating these boundary fragments. The operation is implemented via `scipy.ndimage.binary_erosion` on the integer frame representation. Fragments shorter than the erosion kernel are removed entirely; longer spans are trimmed symmetrically.

The two-step design — dilation of excluded regions followed by erosion of the target region — is conservative by construction: it is always preferable to discard a borderline window than to include one that contaminates the class boundary. The per-file timeline visualisation (Figure S1) makes the effect of both steps directly inspectable, allowing the practitioner to verify that the exclusion logic is behaving as expected for a given annotation density.

S4.5 Per-file reporting

For each audio file processed, Stage 2 writes two output artefacts to the report directory:

- A **Markdown report** (`<stem>_report.md`) summarising the annotation counts, segment counts before and after exclusion and erosion, and the number of windows produced per class.
- A **timeline PNG** (`<stem>_timeline_<class>.png`) showing the label matrix state at each processing step for the target class, in the same format as Figure S1.

These per-file outputs are the primary diagnostic tool for understanding why a particular recording contributed fewer windows than expected. Common causes include a high density of overlapping annotations (producing narrow or zero-length post-exclusion spans), a large proportion of short events filtered by `min_duration`, or file-boundary effects for annotations that begin near the end of a recording.

S4.6 Scroll augmentation

Parameter	Default	Description
<code>stage_2.augmentation.scroll.enabled</code>	<code>false</code>	Global enable flag
<code>stage_2.augmentation.scroll.scroll_step</code>	<code>0.1</code>	Window advance in seconds between consecutive scroll positions

When scroll augmentation is enabled, the sliding-window algorithm is applied with step `scroll_step` instead of the standard `as_overlap`-derived hop. For a `scroll_step` of 0.1 s, a 2-second annotated event yields approximately 12–15 windows instead of the 4–5 that standard windowing would produce, each capturing the vocalization at a slightly different temporal position within the frame. This diversity of spatial positions acts as an implicit positional augmentation, making the trained model less sensitive to the precise temporal alignment of a vocalization within the analysis window.

Scroll augmentation is activated globally via `augmentation.scroll.enabled: true` and can be overridden on a per-class basis via `classes.<name>.augmentation_scroll`. This per-class override is useful when augmentation is needed only for a minority class with few annotated events.

When `center_short_events: true` and `scroll` is simultaneously enabled, `scroll` takes precedence for events shorter than `as_len`.

S5. Stage 3 — Spectrogram Generation (`lib/ai_pam_spectro.py`)

Stage 3 converts each audio window produced by Stage 2 into a spectrogram image ready for CNN input or visual inspection. The conversion follows three steps: computation of the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) using a Hann window, frequency-domain cropping to the bandwidth of interest, and rendering to a fixed-size image via a shared `matplotlib` Figure exported through PIL.

S5.1 FFT parameters

Parameter	Default	Description
<code>stage_3.fft_len</code>	512	FFT window length in samples
<code>stage_3.fft_overlap</code>	0.5	Fractional overlap between consecutive FFT frames (range 0–1)
<code>stage_3.fft_min_freq</code>	3000	Lower frequency bound for spectral cropping (Hz)
<code>stage_3.fft_max_freq</code>	25000	Upper frequency bound for spectral cropping (Hz)

The hop size in samples is $\text{fft_len} \times (1 - \text{fft_overlap})$. The magnitude spectrogram is converted to a dB scale via $20 \log_{10}(|X| + \epsilon)$ with $\epsilon = 1 \times 10^{-10}$ to prevent logarithm of zero. Frequency cropping is performed by discarding STFT magnitude bins outside `[fft_min_freq, fft_max_freq]` before rendering, which both reduces input dimensionality and focuses the CNN on the biologically relevant bandwidth. For *T. truncatus* whistle detection, 3–25 kHz encompasses the typical FM contour range while excluding the dominant low-frequency environmental noise floor.

S5.2 Image output parameters

Parameter	Default	Description
<code>stage_3.image.width_px</code>	224	Output image width in pixels
<code>stage_3.image.height_px</code>	224	Output image height in pixels
<code>stage_3.image.dpi</code>	100	Dots per inch for the rendered figure
<code>stage_3.image.cmap</code>	"gray"	Matplotlib colormap name
<code>stage_3.image.show_axis</code>	false	Include frequency and time axis labels

All spectrogram images are rendered using a singleton `matplotlib` Figure/Axes instance initialised once at startup, avoiding repeated figure allocation overhead during batch export. The rendering pipeline is: STFT computation → frequency slicing → `imshow` on the shared Axes → `fig.canvas.draw()` → RGBA buffer → PIL Image conversion.

Colormap and channel mode. When `cmap` is set to "gray" or any of its variants ("Greys", "gray_r", "Greys_r"), the PIL output mode is "L" (8-bit single-channel grayscale), which is the correct format for a [H, W, 1] CNN input. Any other colormap — "plasma", "viridis", "jet", etc. — produces an "RGB" three-channel output. The output mode is determined once at initialisation and propagates consistently through Stage 4 filters and Stage 5 training, preventing silent channel-count mismatches.

Axis labels. When `show_axis: true`, the image includes frequency (kHz) and time (s) tick marks and axis labels with automatic scaling derived from the STFT parameters. This mode is intended for visual inspection and reporting, not for CNN training, as the axis border area reduces the usable spectrogram region within the fixed pixel budget.

Large-format images for reporting. The `width_px`, `height_px`, and `dpi` parameters can be set to any value independently of the CNN input size. A typical high-resolution report image uses `width_px: 1200`, `height_px: 1200`, `dpi: 150`, `show_axis: true`, and a colour colormap, producing a publication-quality spectrogram with labelled axes that is visually distinct from the compact training images. This configuration is useful for generating figures for papers or monitoring dashboards without modifying the training pipeline configuration.

Important: the `stage_3` parameters — particularly `fft_len`, `fft_min_freq`, `fft_max_freq`, `width_px`, `height_px`, and `image_normalization` — must be identical across the training and cross-test preprocessing runs. Any mismatch produces a systematic input distribution shift that degrades cross-domain performance, often manifesting as a recall collapse that is not accompanied by a change in precision and is therefore difficult to diagnose without comparing the `run_config.yaml` files from both directories side by side.

S6. Stage 4 — Image Preprocessing (`lib/ai_pam_filters.py`)

Stage 4 applies two independent operations to each rendered spectrogram image before it is written to disk: per-image normalisation and an optional OpenCV filter pipeline. Both are controlled entirely via YAML and require no code changes to configure. The stage is optional in the sense that both operations can be disabled (normalization set to `false`, mode set to `none`), but normalisation is enabled by default and its use is recommended for all new experiments.

A complete reference for all supported filters, including YAML schema, parameter descriptions, pipeline modes, compound recipes, and error diagnostics, is provided in `FILTER_REFERENCE.md` at the root of the repository. This section summarises the key concepts and provides two representative examples.

S6.1 Normalisation

Parameter	Default	Description
<code>stage_4.image_normalization</code>	<code>true</code>	Apply min–max normalisation to pixel values

When enabled, pixel intensities are linearly rescaled to [0, 255] independently for each image, using the per-image minimum and maximum as the rescaling bounds. This compensates for amplitude variability across recording sessions, hydrophone sensitivities, and distance-to-source variation, ensuring that the CNN receives inputs with a consistent dynamic range regardless of the absolute signal level in the original recording.

For uniform images ($\text{min} == \text{max}$, which can occur for near-silent segments), the image is returned unchanged to avoid division by zero.

This setting must be identical in the training and cross-test preprocessing runs. A mismatch introduces a systematic input distribution shift that typically manifests as a recall collapse while precision remains unaffected, making the cause difficult to diagnose without comparing the `run_config.yaml` files from both directories.

S6.2 Filter pipeline

Parameter	Default	Description
<code>stage_4.filters.mode</code>	<code>"none"</code>	Filter application mode
<code>stage_4.filters.pipeline</code>	<code>[]</code>	Ordered list of filter specifications

Filter modes.

Value	Behaviour
<code>"none"</code>	No filtering; images passed through normalisation only
<code>"sequential"</code>	Filters applied in order; output of each feeds the next
<code>"mix"</code>	Each filter applied independently to the original; results blended as a weighted sum clipped to [0, 255]

The filter module is built around a generic dispatch mechanism: any `cv2` function is accessible by name without a hardcoded filter list. Two calling conventions are supported — direct filters (the image is passed as the first positional argument) and factory filters (a constructor creates an object, then a method on that object processes the image). The distinction is controlled by the `factory` flag in each pipeline entry.

Each entry in `pipeline` accepts the following fields:

Field	Type	Default	Description
<code>name</code>	<code>str</code>	required	<code>cv2</code> function or

Field	Type	Default	Description
			constructor name
<code>args</code>	list	<code>[]</code>	Positional arguments (after the image for direct filters)
<code>kwargs</code>	dict	<code>{}</code>	Keyword arguments
<code>factory</code>	bool	<code>false</code>	<code>true</code> for constructor-based filters (e.g. <code>createCLAHE</code>)
<code>apply_method</code>	str	<code>"apply"</code>	Method name on factory output
<code>input_convert</code>	str null	<code>null</code>	Force PIL mode conversion before this filter (e.g. <code>"L"</code>)
<code>weight</code>	float	<code>1.0</code>	Blending weight for <code>mix</code> mode

All errors produce a diagnostic block containing the filter name, args, kwargs, and input image shape before raising, allowing diagnosis without a debugger. Common error causes and their fixes are documented in `FILTER_REFERENCE.md §7`.

S6.3 Representative examples

The following two examples illustrate the most common use cases for PAM spectrogram preprocessing. Both are drawn from the recipes in `FILTER_REFERENCE.md`; additional examples covering smoothing, morphological operators, and polarity inversion are provided there.

Example 1 — CLAHE (adaptive contrast enhancement).

CLAHE (Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization) improves local contrast by equalising the pixel intensity histogram within small image tiles, with a configurable clip limit that prevents excessive noise amplification. It is effective on spectrograms with non-uniform background noise, where it makes faint whistle contours more visually prominent without saturating regions of high signal intensity. CLAHE requires single-channel grayscale input; the `input_convert: "L"` field ensures this regardless of the global colormap setting.

```
stage_4:
  image_normalization: true
  filters:
    mode: sequential
    pipeline:
      - name: createCLAHE
        factory: true
        input_convert: "L"
        kwargs:
          clipLimit: 2.0
```

```
tileGridSize: [8, 8]
apply_method: apply
```

Example 2 — CLAHE + Sobel sequential chain (whistle edge enhancement).

This two-step chain first enhances local contrast with CLAHE, then applies a horizontal Sobel operator (first-order derivative in the frequency axis direction) to accentuate the boundary of FM contours. The sequential mode means the Sobel filter receives the CLAHE-processed image, not the original. The `ddepth` value `-1` preserves the input bit depth; using `cv2.CV_64F` (value `6`) instead allows negative gradients, which are then normalised to `uint8` by the module automatically.

```
stage_4:
  image_normalization: true
  filters:
    mode: sequential
    pipeline:
      - name: createCLAHE
        factory: true
        input_convert: "L"
        kwargs:
          clipLimit: 2.0
          tileGridSize: [8, 8]
          apply_method: apply
      - name: Sobel
        args: [-1, 1, 0]      # ddepth=-1, dx=1 (frequency axis), dy=0
        kwargs:
          ksize: 3
```

For a full filter reference including mix-mode recipes, the `bilateralFilter`, `medianBlur`, `Laplacian`, `Scharr`, `equalizeHist`, and `GaussianBlur` filters, and guidance on calling filters directly from Python without YAML, see `FILTER_REFERENCE.md` in the repository root.

S7. Stage 5 — CNN Training (`ai_pam_train.py`)

Stage 5 assembles the spectrogram dataset from the images produced by Stage 4, runs stratified k-fold cross-validation, and writes one trained model per fold together with its performance metrics and diagnostic outputs. The training loop is fully decoupled from the model architecture: the CNN is loaded dynamically from the Python file specified in the YAML, allowing any Keras-compatible architecture to be substituted without modifying the training code.

S7.1 Global training seed

Parameter	Default	Description
<code>stage_5.seed</code>	<code>42</code>	Controls fold partitioning, weight initialisation, and sample shuffling

The seed is re-applied at the start of each fold to ensure that weight initialisation is independently reproducible across folds. Combined with the `run_config.yaml` record, this guarantees that any reported result can be exactly regenerated from the original spectrogram dataset.

S7.2 Model architecture

Parameter	Default	Description
<code>stage_5.model.input_shape</code>	<code>[224, 224, 1]</code>	CNN input dimensions [height, width, channels]; must match Stage 3 image settings
<code>stage_5.model.architecture</code>	<code>models/baseline_cnn.py</code>	Path to a Python file defining <code>build_model(input_shape, n_classes, kernel_size)</code>
<code>stage_5.model.kernel_size</code>	<code>[3, 3]</code>	Convolutional kernel size applied to all blocks

The architecture plug-in convention requires only that the target Python file expose a `build_model(input_shape, n_classes, kernel_size)` function returning an uncompiled `tf.keras.Model`. The training loop calls this function, compiles the model, and manages the rest. Binary models use a sigmoid output unit with binary cross-entropy loss; multiclass models use a softmax output layer with categorical cross-entropy, selected automatically based on the number of classes defined in Stage 2.

Baseline architecture (`models/baseline_cnn.py`). The default model included in the software package is a lightweight Sequential CNN designed for deployment on resource-constrained hardware. It consists of three convolutional blocks with an increasing number of filters (32 → 64 → 128), each followed by ReLU activation and 2×2 max-pooling, then a fully connected head with 128 units and the appropriate output activation. The kernel size is configurable via YAML and is applied uniformly to all convolutional layers.

```
Input [224 × 224 × 1]
Conv2D(32, 3×3, ReLU) → MaxPool(2×2)
Conv2D(64, 3×3, ReLU) → MaxPool(2×2)
Conv2D(128, 3×3, ReLU) → MaxPool(2×2)
Flatten
Dense(128, ReLU)
Dense(1, sigmoid) ← binary
Dense(N, softmax) ← multiclass (N classes)
```

To use a custom architecture, copy `baseline_cnn.py`, edit `build_model`, and point the YAML to the new file:

```
stage_5:
  model:
    architecture: models/my_architecture.py
```

No other configuration change is required.

S7.3 Cross-validation

Parameter	Default	Description
<code>stage_5.cross_validation.k_folds</code>	10	Number of folds
<code>stage_5.cross_validation.stratified</code>	true	Preserve class distribution in each fold
<code>stage_5.cross_validation.max_samples_per_class</code>	null	Cap per class before folding; null = use all available samples

Stratified partitioning is recommended whenever class frequencies differ. For the balanced binary design of experiments — where C0 and C1 are capped to the same number of samples before folding — stratified and standard k-fold are equivalent. For multiclass experiments (five-class, unequal support), stratified partitioning ensures that each fold contains a representative proportion of all classes.

S7.4 Training hyperparameters

Parameter	Default	Description
<code>stage_5.training.epochs</code>	100	Maximum training epochs per fold
<code>stage_5.training.batch_size</code>	32	Mini-batch size
<code>stage_5.training.learning_rate</code>	0.0001	Initial Adam optimiser learning rate
<code>stage_5.training.patience</code>	10	Early stopping patience in epochs
<code>stage_5.training.warmup_epochs</code>	5	Epochs during which early stopping is suppressed
<code>stage_5.training.restore_best_weights</code>	true	Restore weights from the lowest-validation-loss epoch on stopping

Training uses the Adam optimiser with fixed learning rate. Early stopping monitors validation loss with a minimum improvement threshold of 1×10^{-4} ; if no improvement is observed for `patience` consecutive epochs, training halts and the best weights are restored. The `warmup_epochs` parameter suppresses early stopping during the first epochs of training, preventing premature termination during the initial loss plateau that is common in multiclass softmax configurations.

S7.5 Training outputs

Parameter	Default	Description
<code>stage_5.output.model_dir</code>	<code>./outputs/models</code>	Directory for model files and metric records

Parameter	Default	Description
<code>stage_5.output.dataset_dir</code>	<code>./outputs/spectrograms</code>	Spectrogram directory to load; must match <code>output.spectrogram_dir</code>

For each fold, the following files are written to `model_dir`:

- **`fold_NN.keras`** — the trained model at the best-validation-loss epoch, in Keras native format. Used directly by `ai_pam_crosstest.py` for cross-domain evaluation.
- **`fold_NN_metrics.json`** — the complete metric set for the held-out fold: accuracy, precision, recall, F1, macro F1, weighted F1, confusion matrix, and per-class precision/recall/F1.
- **`fold_NN_curves.png`** — training and validation loss and accuracy curves across epochs, with a vertical marker at the best epoch selected by early stopping (Figure S2 below).
- **`fold_NN_report.md`** — a human-readable summary combining the metrics and a text rendering of the confusion matrix.

After all folds complete, a `summary_report.md` is written with cross-fold mean \pm SD for all aggregate metrics.

Figure S2: Training curves for fold 01 of a binary detection experiment. Upper panel: training loss (blue solid) and validation loss (orange dashed). Lower panel: training accuracy and validation accuracy. The vertical dotted line marks the best epoch (epoch 21) at which weights were restored by early stopping. The gap between training and validation loss after epoch 21 reflects continued training beyond the optimal point; the restored weights correspond to the minimum of the validation loss curve.

The training curve is the primary diagnostic for assessing whether a model has converged cleanly. A well-behaved run shows validation loss decreasing monotonically before the best epoch with no divergence between training and validation accuracy, as in Figure S2. Signs of overfitting — a validation loss that stops decreasing or begins to rise while training loss continues to fall — are addressed by reducing `max_samples_per_class`, increasing `patience`, or applying stronger regularisation in the model architecture. Underfitting (both curves plateau at a high loss value) suggests an insufficient learning rate, too few epochs, or a mismatch between `input_shape` and the actual image dimensions.

S8. Stage 6 — Cross-Domain Evaluation (`ai_pam_crosstest.py`)

Stage 6 evaluates the fold models trained in Stage 5 against an independent spectrogram dataset that was not used at any point during training. Cross-domain evaluation is the most demanding test of a PAM model because it exposes the gap between in-domain generalisation — measured by cross-validation on the training corpus — and deployment performance on unseen equipment, sites, and acoustic conditions.

The workflow for Stage 6 consists of three sequential steps: annotating the external audio, generating its spectrogram dataset via a dedicated YAML configuration, and running `ai_pam_crosstest.py` against the trained models.

S8.1 Step 1 — Annotating the external dataset

The external audio must be annotated following the same labelling protocol used for the training corpus (Section S4.2 of this document). Labels are created in Audacity and exported as TSV files using the same stem-matching convention: `recording.flac` → `recording.txt`.

The key requirement at this step is **label vocabulary consistency**: the `include` and `exclude` lists in the cross-test YAML must use the same label strings that appear in the external annotation file. If the external annotator uses different abbreviations (e.g. `W1` instead of `W`), the YAML `include` list must be updated accordingly.

S8.2 Step 2 — Generating the cross-test spectrogram dataset

The cross-test spectrogram dataset is produced by running `ai_pam_preprocessing.py` with a **dedicated configuration file** that differs from the training YAML only in the `input`, `output`, and `report` paths. All Stage 3 and Stage 4 parameters — `fft_len`, `fft_overlap`, `fft_min_freq`, `fft_max_freq`, `image.width_px`, `image.height_px`, `image_normalization` — must be identical to the training configuration. Any mismatch produces a systematic input distribution shift that degrades cross-domain performance in ways that are difficult to diagnose.

An example configuration is reproduced below:

```
experiment_meta:
  name: Binary CNN DCLDE Crosstest
  version: '1.0'
  description: DCLDE Crosstest
```

```

input:
  audio_dir: data/DCLDE/audio      # directory containing the external WAV/FLAC
  files
  label_dir: data/DCLDE/labels     # directory containing the external label files
  audio_glob: '*.flac'
  label_glob: '*.txt'

output:
  spectrogram_dir: outputs/crosstest/spectrograms

report:
  report_dir: outputs/crosstest/report

pipeline:
  stage_1:
    resample_hz: null
    channel:      null
    normalize:    null           # must match the training configuration

  stage_2:
    tl_step:      0.05
    classes:
      C0:
        include: ["NOISE"]
        exclude: ["W", "MW", "W?"]
        min_duration: 0.15
      C1:
        include: ["W", "MW"]
        exclude: ["NOISE", "FB"]
        min_duration: 0.15
    as_len:       0.8
    as_overlap:   0.5
    exclude_overlaps: true
    center_short_events: true
    augmentation:
      scroll:
        enabled:      false
        scroll_step: 0.1

  stage_3:
    fft_len:      512           # must match the training configuration
    fft_overlap:  0.5
    fft_min_freq: 3000
    fft_max_freq: 25000
    image:
      width_px:  224
      height_px: 224
      dpi:        100
      cmap:       gray
      show_axis:  false

  stage_4:
    image_normalization: true     # must match the training configuration
    filters:
      mode:        none
      pipeline:    []

```

Run preprocessing on the external dataset:

```
python ai_pam_preprocessing.py conf/binary_cnn_dclde_crosstest.yaml
```

After completion, verify parameter consistency by comparing the two `run_config.yaml` files:

```
diff outputs/spectrograms/run_config.yaml \
    outputs/crosstest/spectrograms/run_config.yaml
```

The only expected differences are the `input` paths, `output` paths, and `_run_info.timestamp_utc`. Any difference in Stage 3 or Stage 4 parameters indicates a misconfiguration that must be corrected before proceeding.

S8.3 Step 3 — Running the cross-test

With the cross-test spectrograms in place, cross-domain evaluation is launched with:

```
python ai_pam_crosstest.py conf/binary_cnn_512.yaml
```

The script reads the `stage_6.crosstest` block from the training configuration to locate the model directory and test dataset directory, loads all fold models, and evaluates them on the test set according to the specified mode.

Example output for a cross test evaluation, $N_{\text{fft}} = 512$, mode: all:

```
INFO | lib.ai_pam_config | Config loaded - experiment: 'Binary CNN'
INFO | __main__ | Cross-test mode : all
INFO | __main__ | Classes : ['C0', 'C1']
INFO | __main__ | Test dataset dir : crosstest/spectrograms
INFO | __main__ | Model dir : outputs/models
INFO | __main__ | Threshold : 0.5
INFO | __main__ | Discovering test dataset ...
INFO | __main__ | C0: 500 image(s)
INFO | __main__ | C1: 500 image(s)
INFO | __main__ | Total test images : 1000
INFO | __main__ | Found 10 model file(s).
INFO | __main__ | Loading test images ...
=====
INFO | __main__ | Fold 01/10 - fold_01.keras
INFO | __main__ | Accuracy: 0.8910 Macro F1: 0.8897 (2.3s)
[...]
INFO | __main__ | Fold 10/10 - fold_10.keras
INFO | __main__ | Accuracy: 0.8840 Macro F1: 0.8824 (1.9s)
=====
CROSS-TEST COMPLETE - 10 fold model(s)
Accuracy : 0.8760 +/- 0.0092
Macro F1 : 0.8740 +/- 0.0097
Report : crosstest/report/crosstest
=====
```

The header block confirms the evaluation configuration before loading any model. The per-fold lines (one per fold) report accuracy and macro F1 on the 1,000-image balanced test set; their elapsed times (approximately 2 seconds per fold) confirm that Stage 6 is inference-only and does not involve retraining. The summary block reports the cross-fold mean \pm SD.

S8.4 Classification threshold

Parameter	Default	Description
<code>stage_6.evaluation.threshold</code>	0.5	Sigmoid decision threshold for binary classification

For binary models, a sample is assigned to the positive class (C1, whistle present) if the sigmoid output exceeds `threshold`, and to the negative class otherwise. Adjusting this value shifts the precision–recall trade-off: lower values increase recall at the cost of more false positives; higher values increase precision at the cost of missed detections.

For multiclass models, the predicted class is the argmax of the softmax output vector and the `threshold` parameter has no effect.

S8.5 Evaluation modes and additional parameters

Parameter	Default	Description
<code>stage_6.crosstest.test_dataset_dir</code>	null	Directory containing cross-test spectrogram images
<code>stage_6.crosstest.max_samples_per_class</code>	null	Cap per class; null = use all available images
<code>stage_6.crosstest.seed</code>	42	Random seed for balanced sampling
<code>stage_6.crosstest.mode</code>	"all"	Evaluation mode
<code>stage_6.crosstest.report_dir</code>	null	Output directory; null = <code><report.report_dir>/crosstest/</code>
<code>stage_6.crosstest.save_errors</code>	false	Write a TSV of misclassified filenames

Evaluation modes.

Value	Behaviour	Use case
"all"	Each fold model evaluated independently; 10 metric sets produced	Full detailed output
"ensemble"	Sigmoid outputs averaged across all fold models before thresholding	Single stable summary metric for reporting
"best"	Single fold model with highest macro-F1 on the test set	Optimistic upper bound; useful for debugging

"all" and "ensemble" produce complementary views of the same model set and can be run sequentially without retraining.

When `save_errors: true`, an additional TSV file is written listing each misclassified image with its filename, true class, and predicted class. This file is useful for identifying systematic error patterns — for example, whether false negatives are concentrated in short whistles, specific frequency ranges, or particular recording files.

S-UTIL.1 — Spectrogram PDF Catalog (utils/ai_pam_spectrogram_report.py)

Purpose and rationale

Visual inspection of exported spectrogram images is an essential quality-control step between Stage 4 (preprocessing) and Stage 5 (training). Anomalies such as blank images from silent segments, artifacts from boundary effects, or incorrect frequency cropping are immediately apparent on visual examination but invisible to aggregate training metrics — a model trained on a contaminated dataset may achieve plausible accuracy while learning spurious features.

In local workstation environments, spectrogram images can be browsed directly in a file manager. However, in headless computing environments — HPC clusters, SLURM-managed nodes, cloud instances — no graphical display is available. The spectrogram catalog utility addresses this gap by generating self-contained PDF documents that collect all exported spectrograms for a given class into a paginated grid layout. The resulting PDF files can be transferred to a local machine via scp or downloaded from a shared filesystem and examined with any standard PDF viewer.

Usage

The utility reads the spectrogram output directory from the project YAML configuration file and generates one PDF per class:

```
python utils/ai_pam_spectrogram_report.py conf/binary_cnn.yaml
```

Command-line options

Option	Default	Description
<code>--dpi</code>	150	PDF rendering resolution. Higher values produce smaller images on the page, fitting more per sheet.
<code>--classes C0 C1</code>	all	Restrict generation to specific classes.
<code>--max-images N</code>	all	Limit the number of images per class (useful for quick checks).
<code>--max-pages N</code>	50	Maximum pages per PDF file. Larger classes are split into numbered parts.
<code>-v</code>	off	Verbose mode: prints one line per image processed.

Grid layout

The DPI parameter controls the physical size of each spectrogram cell on the page: a 224 × 224 pixel image occupies 224/DPI inches per side. Higher DPI values therefore produce smaller cells and denser grids. For 224 × 224 pixel spectrograms the approximate layout on an A4 page is:

DPI	Cell size (approx.)	Grid (cols × rows)	Images/page	Recommended use
100	~57 mm	3 × 4	~12	Full-size inspection of individual spectrograms
150	~38 mm	4 × 6	~24	Balanced detail for routine quality control
300	~19 mm	9 × 11	~99	Thumbnail overview of large classes

Each image cell includes a truncated filename label for traceability. Page headers display the class name, page number, and total image count.

Output

PDF files are written to the report directory specified in the YAML configuration:

```
<report_dir>/spectrogram_catalog_C0.pdf
<report_dir>/spectrogram_catalog_C0_part2.pdf    (if exceeding max_pages)
<report_dir>/spectrogram_catalog_C1.pdf
```

Dependencies

This utility requires the fpdf2 library:

```
pip install fpdf2
```

The fpdf2 package is included in the project's requirements.txt and is installed automatically with a full dependency install.

Practical recommendations

For a typical binary detection experiment with ~8,000 C0 and ~5,600 C1 images, a DPI of 300 produces compact catalogs of approximately 60 and 40 pages respectively — easily browsable in a single PDF viewer session. At DPI 150 the same classes require roughly 230 and 160 pages, but each spectrogram is large enough to inspect frequency contours in detail.

A recommended quality-control workflow is:

1. Generate a thumbnail overview at DPI 300 with `–max-images 500` to scan for systematic issues (blank images, wrong frequency range, encoding artifacts).
2. If anomalies are detected, regenerate the affected class at DPI 100 to inspect individual spectrograms at full size.
3. After confirming visual quality, proceed to Stage 5 training.

On HPC systems, the catalog generation can be included as a post-processing step in the SLURM preprocessing job:

```
#!/bin/bash
#SBATCH --job-name=pam-preproc
#SBATCH --ntasks=1 --cpus-per-task=4 --mem=16G

source ~/pam_env/bin/activate
python ai_pam_preprocessing.py conf/binary_cnn.yaml -v

# Visual QC catalog (adds ~2 min for 13,000 images at DPI 300)
python utils/ai_pam_spectrogram_report.py conf/binary_cnn.yaml --dpi 300
```

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